

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
STUDENT FEEDBACK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
PROJECT
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ABSTRACT

Description:

The aim of the study was to develop a World Wide Web-based course feedback system serving both students and teachers. The system includes generation and analysis of course feedback pages, provision of feedback, and a summary. Student feedback system is developed for the engineering college students. Students give opinion about their faculty members and vice versa.

The purpose of this feedback system is to gather information on learning experience as well as the about lecturer(s) performance in the class. Student after login into the system, then only is possible to give feedback He has to login with registration number not with the name. He will give the feedback to the faculty member by subject wise. He has five options Excellent, Very good etc. and student has to select one of the five options about faculty in his feedback form. There is a different areas he has to cover individually while giving the feedback like voice strength, Teaching style, Subject knowledge, Behavior and Timing sense. Then He has to submit his feedback with the system. Student can view the Semester results in this system.

Administrator module to avail the facilities college has to register with the system. College user has to append details of the courses offering and branches (EEE, CSE etc). College has to provide Branch name, Branch Code, Course Name and no of Seats. College has to add Faculty members by subject wise, and his/ her full Contact details. They can view details of subjects by branch, Course, Year, Semester and regulation wise. College has to register the students in bulk then they will divide into sections. Student can view the details of results in way of promotion and demotion.

Features:

- This system is developed mainly for the purpose of students to give their feed back about their teachers
- Student can view his/her semester results and grades in this system.
- This system is developed for the exclusively for the engineering colleges students and lecturers.
- Student has to register as a group with a system , it will not accept if student registered individually.
- College can register with the system with branch and faculty details.
- Student has to login with the number not with the name.

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION:

Student feedback system is developed for the exclusively for the purpose of students and lectures. In this system students can view their results semester wise. The purpose of this feedback questionnaire is to gather information on your learning experience, as well as your response(s). When clicking the answer, you have to think of these questions as your subjective perceptions on various aspects of the course and the teacher(s) involved in the program.

The opinion or information provided by the students is useful for the teacher(s) as well as the University in the ongoing efforts and enhance the quality of education. The opinion provided by the student will be kept confidential. The evolution will be calculated on the basis of total scores from the responses from all students. Student(s) has to mention only his register number, need not to mention his name. Student(s) will give their opinion voice strength, teaching style, subject knowledge, and behavior and timing sense. He has select one option from five options (excellent, very good, good, satisfactory, not satisfactory) and also he has to mention faculty name, subject, branch, and department. This information has to submit with the system.

In admin module only college has to register with the system. College has to add branches with the code number and course name. College has to register faculty members with respected course and Department and their total personal details. University or College has to add subject details in particular branch with syllabus. Registered faculty members are appointed to the respective branches. They have to add feedback questions to the system. College has to register in a bulk, and then they have to segregate as groups and allotted sections to them.

Details of Promoted students to next semester will be kept on system. They can view by student id, course name, branch name, section and year. Feedback will be shown in charts and bars format. Then assessment details can be viewed branch, section, course and year. It will give information about faculty members; they have to improve their performance or vice versa will be notified.

Features:

- It is useful to analyze the performance of the faculty members in engineering college.
- Students can view their results, attendance by branch wise and id number.
- Students will give their review about the faculty members in a questionnaire
- Lecturer(s) appointed to the respective departments, with their experience and qualification.
- Administrator will introduce the new colleges to the students and lecturers.

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

SYSTEM:

- Designing and implementing the new links.
- Designing and implementing the users.
- Arranging new links as subject wise.

SYSTEM ANALYSIS:

System analysis will be performed to determine if it is feasible to design information based on policies and plans of the organization and on user requirements and to eliminate the weaknesses of the present system.

- The new system should be cost effective.
- To expand management, improve productivity and services.
- To enhance user / system interface.
- To improve information quality and usability.
- To upgrade systems reliability, availability, flexibility and growth potential.

3.1 Objective of the System:

The main objective of the system is that to provide quality education with proper resources to the students in a reasonable expenditure. Improve the quality of education and also improve the lab facilities, teaching qualities, classroom facilities and other facilities for the students. Main aim is that make available results online for the students they can available 24/7 for the students.

Objectives:-

1. The System is composed with convenient modules of setting and editing the convenient modules for the students to give their opinions about the lecturers and know about the college details.
2. Modules are designed user friendly they can reach anywhere directly without any confusion.
3. This system is designed to save the time and reduce the paper work for taking opinions and making assessments.
4. Administrator will introduce the new colleges to the students to increase the options to the students while joining / selecting the colleges.
5. To improve the quality of education considering the opinions of students.

3.2 User Requirements:

1. User has to register with the system for using all the facilities available in the system
2. Student User has to submit his opinion about his faculty by course, name, subject and department / branch wise.
3. Student can view his results semester wise, it will give the information he/she has promoted/ demoted in the examinations.
4. Student has to login with his id number, which is assigned by the system.
5. College user has to provide details of total number of student, faculty members and contact information.
6. User can view the assessment details by way of charts and bar diagrams and providing course name, branch name, year etc.

7. This system runs any platform; user can access the student id from any place.

3.3 HARDWARE & SOFTWARE SPECIFICATIONS:

HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS:

Processor : Intel P-IV system
Processor Speed : 250MHz to 833MHz
RAM : 512MB RAM
Hard Disk : 40GB

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS:

Operating System : Windows XP
Database : Sql Server
Server side technology : ASP.Net
Server side scripting : ASP
Client side scripting : HTML
Web-Server : IIS

SOFTWARE DESIGN

4.1 UML DIAGRAMS

UML Diagrams

4.1.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM:

- A use case diagram is a diagram that shows a set of use cases and actors and relationships.

Contents

- Use case commonly contain
 - Use cases
 - Actors
 - Dependency, generalization and association relationships

Overall Use Case

Administrator Use Case

Student Use Case

Class Diagram

4.1.2 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM:

- An activity diagram shows the flow from activity to activity. An activity is an ongoing non- atomic execution within a state machine.
- Activities ultimately result in some action, which is made up of executable atomic computations that result in a change in state of the system or the return of a value. Activity diagrams commonly contain
 - Activity states and action states
 - Transitions
 - Objects
- Like all other diagrams, activity diagrams may contain notes and constrains.

Student Process

Administrator Process

4.1.4 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

- An interaction diagram shows an interaction, consisting of a set of objects and their relationships, including the messages that may be dispatched among them.
- A sequence diagram is an interaction diagram that emphasizes the time ordering of messages.
- Graphically, a sequence diagram is a table that shows objects arranged along x-axis and messages, ordered in increasing time, along the y-axis.

Contents

- Sequence diagrams commonly contain the following:
 - Objects
 - Links
 - Messages

Like all other diagrams, sequence diagrams may contain notes and constrains.

Administrator Sequence

Student Sequence

DATABASE DESIGN

Faculty Details

SQL Server Enterprise Manager - [Design Table 'Faculty_Details' in 'StudentFeedBackSystem' on '(LOCAL)']

Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
FacultyName	varchar	50	
CourseName	varchar	50	✓
FacultyId	nvarchar	50	
Department	varchar	50	✓
Address	varchar	20	✓
EmailId	nvarchar	50	✓
Mobile	nvarchar	50	✓
Remarks	varchar	20	✓

Columns

Description

Default Value

Precision 0

Scale 0

Identity No

Identity Seed

Identity Increment

Is RowGuid No

Formula

Collation <database default>

Feedback Details

The screenshot displays the SQL Server Enterprise Manager interface for designing a table named 'Feedback_Details' in the 'StudentFeedBackSystem' database on '(LOCAL)'. The main window shows a table design grid with the following columns:

Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
Question	varchar	100	
FacultyName	varchar	50	✓
BranchName	varchar	50	✓
Subject	varchar	50	✓
FeedBack	varchar	50	✓
[Year]	char	18	✓
Semester	varchar	20	✓
[Section]	varchar	50	✓
StudentId	nvarchar	50	✓
Department	nvarchar	50	✓

Below the grid, the 'Columns' tab is active, showing the properties for the selected 'Question' column:

Property	Value
Description	
Default Value	
Precision	0
Scale	0
Identity	No
Identity Seed	
Identity Increment	
Is RowGuid	No
Formula	
Collation	<database default>

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the Start button and several open applications: SFS - Microsoft..., SQL Query Anal..., Gmail - Compos..., SQL Server Ent..., and Database - Mic... The system clock indicates 10:42 AM.

Question Details

The screenshot shows the SQL Server Enterprise Manager interface. The main window displays the design view of a table named 'Question_Details' in the 'StudentFeedbackSystem' database on the '(LOCAL)' server. The table has two columns: 'QuestionId' and 'Question'. The 'QuestionId' column is of type 'int' with a length of 4 and is marked as 'Allow Nulls' (checked). The 'Question' column is of type 'varchar' with a length of 100. Below the table design, the 'Columns' pane is visible, showing properties for the selected column. The properties include: Description, Default Value, Precision (10), Scale (0), Identity (No), Identity Seed, Identity Increment, Is RowGuid (No), Formula, and Collation.

Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
QuestionId	int	4	✓
Question	varchar	100	

Columns

Description
Default Value
Precision: 10
Scale: 0
Identity: No
Identity Seed
Identity Increment
Is RowGuid: No
Formula
Collation

Student Details

The screenshot displays the SQL Server Enterprise Manager interface for designing a table named 'Student_Details' in the 'StudentFeedBackSystem' database on a local instance. The main window shows a table design grid with the following columns:

Column Name	Data Type	Length	Allow Nulls
StudentId	nvarchar	50	
Password	nvarchar	50	✓
CourseName	varchar	50	✓
BranchName	nvarchar	50	✓
AdmissionType	nvarchar	50	✓
AcademicYear	nvarchar	50	✓
[Year]	int	4	✓
Semester	varchar	20	✓
[Section]	varchar	50	✓

Below the grid, the 'Columns' tab is active, showing the properties for the selected column:

- Description: [Empty]
- Default Value: [Empty]
- Precision: 0
- Scale: 0
- Identity: No
- Identity Seed: [Empty]
- Identity Increment: [Empty]
- Is RowGuid: No
- Formula: [Empty]
- Collation: <database default>

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the Start button and several open applications: SFS - Microsoft..., SQL Query Anal..., Gmail - Compos..., SQL Server Ent..., and Database - Mic... The system clock indicates 10:42 AM.

INPUT AND OUTPUT SCREENS

Student Module

Student Login Page

Feedback form

Untitled Page - Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/FeedBack.aspx

Most Visited Getting Started Latest Headlines

STUDENT FEEDBACK SYSTEM

[Home](#)
[Feedback](#)
[Change Password](#)
[Logout](#)

1 Voice strength?

Excellent, Very Good, Good, Satisfactory, Not Satisfactory					FacultyName	Subject	Branch	Department
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	anil	English	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Kumar	Mathematics-1	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Phani	Solid State Physics	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Praveen	Information Technology & Numerical Methods	EEE	CSE

Done

start SFS (Running) - Micro... SFS Screens - Micro... Untitled Page - Mozil... SQL Query Analyzer 10:10 AM

Untitled Page - Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/FeedBack.aspx

Most Visited Getting Started Latest Headlines

Excellent	Good	Good	Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Phani	Mathematics I	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Phani	Solid State Physics	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Praveen	Information Technology & Numerical Methods	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	raja	Electronic Devices and Circuits	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	ram	Engineering Drawing Practice	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Revanth	C & Data structures	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Sai	Electronic Devices & Circuits Lab	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	sajith	Network Theory	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Satish	Computer Programming Lab	EEE	CSE

Next

Done

start SFS (Running) - Micro... SFS Screens - Micro... Untitled Page - Mozill... SQL Query Analyzer 10:10 AM

Untitled Page - Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/FeedBack.aspx

Most Visited Getting Started Latest Headlines

2 Teaching Style?

Excellent, Very Good, Good, Satisfactory, Not Satisfactory	FacultyName	Subject	Branch	Department
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	anil	English	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	Kumar	Mathematics-1	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	Phani	Solid State Physics	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	Praveen	Information Technology & Numerical Methods	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	raja	Electronic Devices and Circuits	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	ram	Engineering Drawing Practice	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	Revanth	C & Data structures	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	Sai	Electronic Devices & Circuits Lab	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	sajith	Network Theory	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent ☐ Very Good ☐ Good ☐ Satisfactory ☐ Not Satisfactory	Satish	Computer Programming Lab	EEE	CSE

Done

start SFS (Running) - Micro... SFS Screens - Micro... Untitled Page - Mozill... SQL Query Analyzer 10:13 AM

Untitled Page - Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/FeedBack.aspx

Most Visited Getting Started Latest Headlines

3 Subject Knowledge?

Excellent,Very Good,Good,Satisfactory,Not Satisfactory					FacultyName	Subject	Branch	Department
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	anil	English	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Kumar	Mathematics-1	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Phani	Solid State Physics	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Praveen	Information Technology & Numerical Methods	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	raja	Electronic Devices and Circuits	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	ram	Engineering Drawing Practice	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Revanth	C & Data structures	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Sai	Electronic Devices & Circuits Lab	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	sajith	Network Theory	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Satish	Computer Programming Lab	EEE	CSE

Done

start SFS (Running) - Micro... SFS Screens - Micro... Untitled Page - Mozill... SQL Query Analyzer 10:13 AM

Untitled Page - Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/FeedBack.aspx

Most Visited Getting Started Latest Headlines

4 Behaviour?

Excellent,Very Good,Good,Satisfactory,Not Satisfactory					FacultyName	Subject	Branch	Department
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	anil	English	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Kumar	Mathematics-1	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Phani	Solid State Physics	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Praveen	Information Technology & Numerical Methods	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	raja	Electronic Devices and Circuits	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	ram	Engineering Drawing Practice	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Revanth	C & Data structures	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Sai	Electronic Devices & Circuits Lab	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	sajith	Network Theory	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Satish	Computer Programming Lab	EEE	CSE

Done

start SFS (Running) - Micro... SFS Screens - Micro... Untitled Page - Mozill... SQL Query Analyzer 10:14 AM

Untitled Page - Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/FeedBack.aspx

Most Visited Getting Started Latest Headlines

STUDENT FEEDBACK SYSTEM

[Home](#) [Feedback](#) [Change Password](#) [Logout](#)

5 Timinig Sence?

Excellent	Very Good	Good	Satisfactory	Not Satisfactory	FacultyName	Subject	Branch	Department
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	anil	English	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Kumar	Mathematics-1	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Phani	Solid State Physics	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Praveen	Information Technology & Numerical Methods	EEE	CSE

Done

start SFS (Running) - Micro... SFS Screens - Micro... Untitled Page - Mozill... SQL Query Analyzer 10:15 AM

Untitled Page - Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Tools Help

http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/FeedBack.aspx

Most Visited Getting Started Latest Headlines

☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	anil	English	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Kumar	Mathematics-1	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Phani	Solid State Physics	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Praveen	Information Technology & Numerical Methods	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	raja	Electronic Devices and Circuits	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	ram	Engineering Drawing Practice	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Revanth	C & Data structures	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Sai	Electronic Devices & Circuits Lab	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	sajith	Network Theory	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Satish	Computer Programming Lab	EEE	CSE

Done

start SFS (Running) - Micro... SFS Screens - Micro... Untitled Page - Mozil... SQL Query Analyzer 10:15 AM

Feedback submitted

The screenshot shows a Mozilla Firefox browser window displaying a feedback form at the URL `http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/FeedBack.aspx`. The form contains a table with columns for feedback options (Excellent, Very Good, Good, Satisfactory, Not Satisfactory), student names, course names, and department codes (EEE, CSE). A modal dialog box titled "Student FeedBack System" is overlaid on the form, displaying the message "FeedBack Submitted" and an "OK" button. The browser's taskbar at the bottom shows several open applications, including "SPS (Running)", "SPS Screens - M...", "Untitled Page - ...", "SQL Query Anal...", and "Student FeedBa...". The system clock indicates the time is 10:15 AM.

Feedback	Feedback	Feedback	Feedback	Feedback	Name	Examinations	EEE	EEE
☒ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Phani	Solid State Physics	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☒ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Praveen	Information Technology & Numerical Methods	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☒ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	raja	Electronic Devices and Circuits	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☒ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	ram	Engineering Drawing Practice	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☒ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory		ta structures	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☒ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory		ic Devices & Circuits Lab	EEE	EEE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☐ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☒ Not Satisfactory	sajith	Network Theory	EEE	CSE
☐ Excellent	☐ Very Good	☒ Good	☐ Satisfactory	☐ Not Satisfactory	Satish	Computer Programming Lab	EEE	CSE

Feedback sent successfully

Change Password

The screenshot shows a Mozilla Firefox browser window displaying the 'Change Password' page of a 'STUDENT FEEDBACK SYSTEM'. The browser's address bar shows the URL 'http://localhost:1664/SFS/Stud/ChangePassword.aspx'. The page features a navigation menu with links for 'Home', 'Feedback', 'Change Password', and 'Logout'. Below the menu, there are three input fields for 'Old Password', 'New Password', and 'Confirm New Password', followed by a 'Save' button. The page is framed by a pink border.

STUDENT FEEDBACK SYSTEM

[Home](#) [Feedback](#) [Change Password](#) [Logout](#)

Old Password :

New Password :

Confirm New Password :

Administrator Module

College Registration

The screenshot shows a Mozilla Firefox browser window with the address bar displaying `http://localhost:1664/SFS/Admin/CollegeRegistration.aspx`. The page content is titled "STUDENT FEEDBACK SYSTEM" and features a header image of a computer lab. Below the image is a registration form with the following fields and buttons:

College Registration
Fill the following Form for the Registration

College Name :
College Code :
Established Year :

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the Start button and several open applications: SPS - Microsoft Visual..., SFS Screens - Micro..., SQL Query Analyzer, and the current browser window. The system clock shows 10:16 AM.

Admin_Login

Adding Branches

The screenshot shows a Mozilla Firefox browser window displaying the 'STUDENT FEEDBACK SYSTEM' admin interface. The page title is 'STUDENT FEEDBACK SYSTEM'. The browser address bar shows 'http://localhost:1664/SFS/Admin/Branch.aspx'. The page features a navigation menu with links: Home, Faculty, Subjects, Assign, Question, Section, Charts, Student, Branch, Reports, Promote, Assessment, Logout. The main content area includes a form for adding a new branch. The 'Course Name' field has two radio buttons: 'B.Tech' (selected) and 'M.Tech'. The 'Branch Name' and 'Branch Code' fields are empty text boxes. Below the form are 'Save' and 'Reset' buttons. A table displays existing branches:

Select Branch	BranchCode	BranchName	CourseName
Delete	02	EEE	B.Tech
Delete	05	CSE	B.Tech

Below the table, it states: '2 No of Branches are Available.'

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the Start button and several open applications: SFS (Running) - Micro..., SFS Screens - Micros..., SQL Query Analyzer, and the current browser window. The system clock shows 10:18 AM.

CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION

Normally conventional system we use maximum manual applications. It consumes lots of time and paper. But this system totally Web based, it means that student can enter into the system very easily. They can view the details of the colleges affiliated under JNTU University and their contact information. This system is totally user friendly and timesaving and cost effective system. All the modules are designed in a way that a layman can understand the system very easily. Student /college can reach the place where they want to reach in a very minimum amount of time.

Future enhancements:

- The complete project is to be web-based
- The student can view Results and assessment details online.
- All the services are provided in online
- College / Student user access the system staying anywhere

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8. REFERENCES AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

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